

D.6.5 Design of gender-sensitive print and online media for awareness raising activities

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GEARING ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
PGA	Participatory Gender Audit
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
WP	Work Package

Introduction

This document provides guidance and suggestions, in the form of infographics, for the use of innovative tools and materials in the GEARING-Roles project's GEP implementing partners. These infographics are designed to support the process of deconstructing gender roles in higher education that is integral to the GEARING-Roles project. The infographics outline issues around women's and men's representation in higher education (and particularly STEM subjects), their working conditions, access to leadership positions and how gender is mainstreamed in research. They provide easily communicable data to communicate key gender-related issues to senior leaders and other key stakeholders within each of the GEP partners' institutions, while also providing a useful benchmark and comparison with other contexts. These infographics will also be shared on social media to raise awareness of key issues in a broader context.

Infographics for awareness raising among senior leaders and other key stakeholders in presenting GEPs

Within the project, a key objective is the deconstruction of gender roles. The project aims to do this by raising awareness of what these gender roles are and how internalised and unchallenged behaviours, perceptions, and practices related to gender and what this means, perpetuate gender inequalities.

The GEAR tool¹ illustrates how implicit bias operates, and encourages organisations to challenge cultural stereotypes and reconsider the reasons behind individual and institutional decisions. With this in mind, GEARING-Roles considers that a viable approach to tackling implicit bias is to understand the sociology and psychology of gender roles, challenge them, and move towards eliminating their effects on equality. GEARING roles will thus reinforce a gender-sensitive perspective in research and research institutions, including in their every-day teaching and campus life.

Pictures, infographics, and audiovisual materials are important communication tools to influence perceptions, attitudes and social change. These materials will be shared in the project's social media channels as part of a campaign that raises the visibility of some key gender equality issues in higher

¹ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear>

education in the six countries of GEP implementing partners. These resources are designed to be used as a stand-alone document, but can also be shared online or displayed on screens as part of presentations or events.

These infographics complement the institutional assessment process undertaken as part of WP3 (institutional reports for all six GEP implementers; participatory gender audits (PGAs); comparative report). They are designed to assist GEP implementers, using key data sources, by providing a tool to easily communicate to senior leaders and other key stakeholders on gender equality issues in higher education. These infographics provide an overview of the situation in the national context and thus allow for a benchmark of the institution. They also provide information about data gaps where relevant. Finally, these infographics allow for a comparison between different country contexts.

The aim of these infographics is to provide high-quality data (or highlight data gaps) in key areas, mapping onto the areas of focus of the GEARING-Roles project (WP4 on careers, WP5 on leadership and WP6 on mainstreaming gender in research). The infographics showcase the representation of women and men as doctoral students, demonstrating that if progress has been made in this respect overall, representation remains low in STEM. The data then show how women are under-represented as scientists, researchers and engineers compared with men. They also provide information on women's greater likelihood in some countries to work on a part-time basis, to be employed under 'precarious' contracts, to be paid less than men and to be less represented in more senior positions. Information on the prevalence of GEPs shows different situations across GEP implementing partners' countries, with some having a long history of implementing gender institutional change while others' experiences may be more limited. This is demonstrating the need to learn from each other's experiences. The infographics conclude with data on the potential effects of gender inequalities, particularly in STEM-related fields, for the content of research. Data examine gender inequalities as authors and inventors, but also in funding received.

Below we provide a description of how each of the 15 infographics provided can be used in communication with senior leaders and other stakeholders.

Section 1 – this section provides key data on the pool of graduate talent

1. The first infographic provides an overview of the proportion of women as doctoral graduates in the six GEP implementing partners' countries in 2016. This shows that overall, there is approximate parity across all countries. The most notable data point is Slovenia where women are slightly over-represented as doctoral graduates (61%).
2. The second infographic compares the overall proportion of women as doctoral graduates (infographic 1) to the proportion of women doctoral graduates in information and communication technologies. It can be used to show the much lower representation of women in this area, ranging from just 13% in Estonia to 44% in Turkey.
3. The third infographics compares the overall proportion of women as doctoral graduates (infographic 1) to the proportion of women doctoral graduates in physical sciences. It shows a lower proportion in some countries such as the UK (36%), but a higher proportion of women in other countries such as Slovenia (62%).

Section 2 – this section provides key data on employment as scientists, engineers or researchers

4. The fourth infographic compares the proportions of women and men as scientists and engineers among the total labour force in 2017. It shows that some countries have a higher proportion of scientists (greatest in the UK and lowest in Turkey), which provides information on the innovation ecosystem of respective countries. It also shows that in some countries (Estonia, Slovenia and the UK), men are much more represented in these professions than women.
5. The fifth infographic looks only at the proportion of researchers among the total labour force in 2015. These data show that as researchers, women are under-represented compared with men in all countries with the exception of Turkey.
6. The sixth infographic provides further information specifically about researchers in the higher education sector and in the engineering and technology subject area of higher education. It demonstrates that if women are relatively well represented overall in higher education (from 42% in Spain to 49% in Portugal), their representation in engineering and technology drops significantly in engineering and technology (from 23% in the UK to 38% in Spain).
7. The seventh infographic looks at part-time employment for researchers in higher education by sex in 2016. It shows that in Estonia or the UK, women researchers are much more likely to work part-time. This contrasts with Spain or Portugal, where the reverse is true. It also shows a data gap for Turkey.
8. The eighth infographic examines the proportions of ‘precarious’ working contracts in higher education by sex in 2016. These are lowest in the UK. In Estonia, Portugal and the UK, it is clear that women are disproportionately affected. The opposite is true in Spain. There is a data gap for Turkey.
9. The ninth infographic presents data on the gender pay gap. It shows that there is only a 3.5% gender pay gap in Slovenia, compared to a much wider gap of 35.7% in Turkey.
10. The tenth infographic shows how polarized countries are when it comes to having RPOs where gender equality plans have been implemented. It is only in Spain and the UK that gender equality plans have been implemented, with coverage of the majority of RPOs. In the UK, this reflects the effect of the Athena SWAN process for example. Nonetheless, even where a GEP is mandatory, it should be noted that their existence does not say anything about their content or state of implementation.
11. The eleventh infographic turns to women’s and men’s representation at different (academic) grades in 2016. It clearly shows that in all countries (except Estonia where there are no data), there is a significant drop from Grade D (the lowest grade) to Grade A (the highest grade). This drop goes from a range of approximate parity or more for women (from about 50% to 60%) to less than critical mass (from about 20% to 30%).
12. The twelfth infographic extends this by showing the proportion of women among heads of institutions in the higher education sector in 2017. In some countries such as Spain or Turkey, the proportion of women in such positions is very low with 8% and 9% respectively.

Section 3 – this section provides key data on gender and the content of research and innovation

13. The thirteenth infographic compares the women to men ratio of authorships of academic articles in all fields of R&D compared with authorships in engineering and technology for the period 2013 to 2017. These data show that in all countries, women are much less likely to be

listed as authors than men. Further, it shows that this is even lower in a subject area like engineering and technology.

14. The fourteenth infographic examines the women to men ratio of inventors for the same period of time. Inventorship is measured through a count of patent applications, on a fractional basis in cases where there are several people involved. The ratio clearly demonstrates that women are greatly under-represented as inventors, compared with men, in all six countries.
15. The fifteenth infographic shows that men are more likely to be successful in securing research funding in most countries. The gender gap in funding is calculated as the success rate of men team leaders minus the success rate for women team leaders. Where the difference is positive, this can be interpreted as a higher success rate for men, and conversely. When comparing with research funding in engineering and technology, success rates in Estonia are much larger for men than women (18.7 percentage points difference). There is a data gap in Turkey.

Annex I – Infographics

Infographic 1

Proportion women doctoral graduates 2016

- EE: 54%
- ES: 51%
- PT: 55%
- SI: 61%
- UK: 46%
- TR: 46%

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 20

Infographic 2

Proportion women doctoral graduates 2016 in information and communication technologies

- EE: 13%
- ES: 22%
- PT: 28%
- SI: 24%
- UK: 24%
- TR: 44%

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 23

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Infographic 3

Proportion women doctoral graduates 2016 in physical sciences

- EE: 44%
- ES: 51%
- PT: 56%
- SI: 62%
- UK: 36%
- TR: 49%

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 26

Infographic 4

Proportions of scientists and engineers among the total labour force by sex 2017

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 40

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Infographic 5

Proportion of researchers per thousand labour force by sex 2015

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 62

Infographic 6

Proportion of women among researchers 2015

Higher education

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 65

Higher education (engineering and technology)

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 78

Infographic 7

Proportion of part-time employment of researchers in higher education by sex 2016

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 97

Infographic 8

Proportion of 'precarious' working contracts in higher education by sex 2016

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 99

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Infographic 9

Infographic 10

Infographic 11

Proportion of women and men by grade 2016

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 118

Infographic 12

Proportion of women among heads of institutions in the Higher Education Sector 2017

- EE: 30%
- ES: 8%
- PT: 29%
- SI: 32%
- UK: 24%
- TR: 9%

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 128

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Infographic 13

Women to men ratio of authorships in all fields of R&D and in engineering and technology 2013-17

- EE: 0.61, 0.4
- ES: 0.67, 0.5
- PT: 0.78, 0.6
- SI: 0.59, 0.5
- UK: 0.51, 0.3
- TR: 0.55, 0.4

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 138

Infographic 14

Women to men ratio of inventorships 2013-17

- EE: 0.16
- ES: 0.20
- PT: 0.25
- SI: 0.15
- UK: 0.11
- TR: 0.16

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 167

Infographic 15

Research funding success rate differences between women and men total and in engineering and technology 2017

- EE: 5.1, 18.7
- ES: 4.9, 4
- PT: 0.2, 0.4
- SI: 3.6, 1.1
- UK: 1.3, -
- TR: /

Source: She Figures 2018, p. 173

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